

Vanadium. Part V. Vanadium (IV) and Vanadium (V) Complexes of Substituted Hydroxytriazenes

R. L. Dutta and Subrata Lahiry

Preparation and properties of vanadium(IV) and vanadium(V) complexes of a large number of substituted hydroxytriazenes have been reported. The quadrivalent vanadium complexes conform to the composition $[VO_2T_2]$ (where TH = a molecule of the ligand). These are paramagnetic [$\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.6-2.1$ B.M.]. Cryoscopic measurements in freezing benzene reveal their monomeric nature. These complexes react with pyridine or α -picoline(X) resulting in an oxidised product $[VO_2T.X]$. These are diamagnetic. Most of these yellow-coloured complexes dissolve in benzene from which green compounds of identical composition have been recovered and a few others lose their heterocyclic base, affording $[VO_2T]$. Some of the ligands used have been reported here for the first time.

In the preceding part¹ we have reported some complexes of vanadium (IV) and of vanadium(V) with 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene. We have succeeded in adducing convincing proof that the ligand brings about the reduction of vanadium (V) to vanadium (IV), which then forms a deep olive-green complex of the type (VO_2T_2) (where, TH = a molecule of the ligand). This compound was, however, oxidised in a basic medium, such as, pyridine, α -picoline, or aniline, to a golden yellow product $(VO_2T.X)$ (where X = a molecule of the heterocyclic base). The golden yellow product further changed in benzene to furnish a deep greenish black product of the same empirical composition.

We have now extended the study to a large number of variedly substituted hydroxytriazenes and confirmed our earlier findings. The following substituted derivatives have been investigated as complexing ligands:

- I. N^3 -Phenyl: N^1 -*p*-methyl-, *p*-nitro-, *p*-ethoxy-, *p*-benzoyl-, *p*-carboxy-, *p*-sulphonamido-, *m*-bromo-, *m*-nitro-, *o*-nitro-*, and *o*-methoxy-*phenyl.
- II. N^3 -*p*-Methylphenyl: N^1 -phenyl-, *p*-methyl-, and *p*-nitro-phenyl.
- III. N^3 -Methyl: N^1 -phenyl, *p*-methyl-, *p*-ethoxy-, and *p*-nitro-phenyl, and β -naphthyl.

Some of these reagents were not reported earlier in the literature. The pertinent characteristics of these new reagents are recorded in Table I.

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-methylphenyl-3-phenyltriazene reacts with vanadyl sulphate in aqueous ethanol medium, furnishing deep olive-green, shining crystals which correspond

to the composition, $[\text{VO}_2]_2$ ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.69 \text{ B.M.}$) (where T.H = a molecule of the ligand). A similar compound is also obtained by addition of aqueous ammonium vanadate to an excess of the ligand in ethanol medium at pH 2-3 (ca.). This too provides analytical figures for $(\text{VO}_2^+)_2$ ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.58 \text{ B.M.}$). Both the preparations therefore are to be regarded as containing vanadium in quadrivalent state. It will be appreciated here that in cases of compounds with such reducing ligands, direct titrimetric determination of the oxidation state is not possible. Further, we have obtained the I. R. spectra of both the samples in nujol. These have been found to be identical. Both reveal strong vanadyl bands in the vicinity of 978 cm^{-1} with shoulder at 963 cm^{-1} . Their appreciable solubility in benzene was utilised for cryoscopic determination of molecular size. The values 490 and 510 are in agreement with the monomeric formula (calc. 519). This observation provides strong evidence against polymeric structure.

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-ethoxyphenyl-3-phenyltriazene and 3-hydroxy-1-phenyl-3-*p*-methylphenyltriazene also reduce vanadium(v) to vanadium(IV) and yield the vanadium(IV) complex. The latter is identical with the preparation from vanadyl sulphate. A large number of other ligands, excepting the ones marked with an asterisk, did produce yellowish green to light olive-green products with vanadyl sulphate, but failed to furnish well-defined compounds from ammonium vanadate. The products are all quadrivalent and show μ_{eff}^* values of the order 1.6-2.1 B.M. Molecular weights of some of these were determined in freezing benzene. A few others, which were found to be poorly soluble in benzene, may also be considered to be monomeric in nature.

The ligands, marked with an asterisk above, failed to produce any well-defined pure compound either with vanadyl sulphate or with ammonium vanadate. Substitution in *ortho* position to the *-N-* atom definitely reduced the complex-forming capacity of the ligand.

The behaviour of the quadrivalent vanadium complexes, described above, towards organic bases, such as, pyridine, α -picoline, etc., has also been investigated. The compound, oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-*p*-methylphenyl-3-phenyltriazene-vanadium (IV), on warming with pyridine, dissolves, forming a brown solution from which a yellow crystalline compound is obtained. This on analysis is found to have the composition $(\text{VO}_2\text{T}^*\text{py})_2$. The compound is diamagnetic, indicating presence of vanadium in the quinquivalent state. The compound dissolves in ethanol to a yellow solution, whereas in benzene the initial yellow colour changes within a few minutes to deep green. The fairly appreciable solubility of the compound in benzene allowed us to make cryoscopic determination of its molecular size. This was found to be a monomer.

The quadrivalent vanadium complexes of the following substituted hydroxytriazenes of the types ;

- I. N^3 -Phenyl : *N*¹-*p*-methyl- and -*p*-nitro-phenyl
- II. N^3 -*p*-Methylphenyl : *N*¹-phenyl
- III. N^3 -Methyl : *N*¹-*p*-methyl- and -*p*-ethoxy-phenyl

are found to react with pyridine to form well-defined yellow to orange-red compounds of the type $(\text{VO}_2\text{T}^*\text{py})_2$.

* $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 [\frac{1}{2}n(n+2)]^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

The bright yellow compound of *N*³-phenyl: *N*¹-*p*-methylphenyl of type (I) above dissolves in a large volume of pure benzene, forming after sometime a green solution from which a dark green powder of the composition (VO₂T'py) is obtained. The analyses are against the formation of any π-type complex with benzene. The golden yellow compound does not suffer any loss at 100° even after 8-10 hours, although the colour changes to brownish green, indicating that the isomeric change is also brought about through heating. The yellow vanadium(v) complex of *N*³-phenyl-*N*¹-*p*-nitrophenyl of type (I) is less soluble in benzene from which a light greenish yellow variety can be recovered. The yellow-coloured complex (VO₂T'py) of the ligand *N*³-methyl: *N*¹-*p*-methylphenyl of type (III) also dissolves in benzene. On allowing it to stand for 4 hours, the green solution deposits, unlike the others, a light bottle-green precipitate. The analyses fit the formula (VO₂T') of the compound which is diamagnetic. The original yellow pyridine-containing preparation on heating at 100° for about 15 hours loses pyridine, corresponding to the composition (VO₂T') and turns light bottle-green. The solubility of the bright orange-yellow compound (VO₂T'py) (where T'H = *N*³-methyl: *N*¹-*p*-ethoxyphenyl of type III) in benzene is low and no ready transformation has been observed. When the orange-yellow compound is heated at 100° for 16 hours, pyridine is lost and the colour changes to brownish green.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general method of synthesis of the reagents²⁻⁴ was the same as described in the earlier part¹. Some of the reagents, however, separated from the reaction medium as semisolid or sometimes oily products. Compound No. 7 (Table I) separated as a brown oil which was removed from the reaction mixture, washed well with water and then with a little ethanol when it assumed an orange colour and a granular nature. This was first purified from boiling petroleum and then from benzene, when the cream-coloured compound was obtained. Compound No. 6 also separated as a red-coloured oil which on scratching in presence of water turned into a semisolid mass. This was treated with a little ethanol when a red crystalline mass was obtained. This was finally purified from a small volume of acetone.

TABLE I

$$\text{R}-\overset{\text{V}}{\underset{\text{OH}}{\text{N}}}=\text{N}-\overset{\text{N}}{\text{N}}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$$

No.	Compound. (R=)	Cryst. from.	M.P.	Appearance.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>p</i> -(OC ₂ H ₅).C ₆ H ₄	Acetone	112-13°	Yellow flakes	16.30	16.40
2	<i>p</i> -(COC ₆ H ₅).C ₆ H ₄	Benzene	160-62°	Light yellow	13.10	13.29
3	<i>p</i> -(SO ₂ NH ₂).C ₆ H ₄ (H ₂ O)	EtOH-acetone	178-80°	Cream-white	17.80	18.12
4	<i>m</i> -(Br).C ₆ H ₄	EtOH	148-50°	Buff	14.95	14.43
5	<i>m</i> -(NO ₂).C ₆ H ₄	Benzene	176-78°	Light yellow	21.71	21.79
6	<i>o</i> -(NO ₂).C ₆ H ₄	Acetone	150°	Orange-red	21.20	21.79
7	<i>o</i> -(OCH ₃).C ₆ H ₄	Benzene	108-10°	Cream	16.90	17.35

(First from petroleum and then from benzene)

- Gebhard and Thompson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 85, 767.
- Elkins and Hunter, *ibid.*, 1938, 1346.
- Sogani and Bhattacharya, *this Journal*, 1959, 36, 563.

1. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-methylphenyl-3-phenyltriazene-vanadium* (IV).—(A). Vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g. in 5-10ml water) was added to an ethanolic solution (80 ml) of the reagent (0.6 g.). The clear green solution changed to brown on shaking and deposited olivogreen, shining crystals. These were then filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . (Found: V, 9.61; N, 16.50; C, 60.52; H, 4.37; M.W., 490. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O})_2]$ requires V, 9.82; N, 16.18; C, 60.11; H, 4.62%; M.W., 519) χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1195$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.69$ B.M.

(B). Ammonium vanadate (0.1 g. in 5-10 ml water) was added to an ethanolic solution (80 ml) of the reagent (0.8 g.). This was then acidified with a few drops of H_2SO_4 (ca. 2N) to a pH 2-3. The resulting solution on keeping deposited crystals of the characteristic olivogreen vanadium complex. (Found: V, 9.65; N, 16.42%; M.W., 510). χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1038$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.58$ B.M.

2. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-ethoxyphenyl-3-phenyltriazene-vanadium* (IV) was obtained both from vanadyl sulphate and from ammonium vanadate in aqueous ethanolic medium by following the procedures described above.

(A). From VOSO_4 : (Found: V, 8.60; N, 14.57%; M.W., 565. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)]$ requires V, 8.80; N, 14.51%; M.W., 579). χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1247$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.73$ B.M.

(B). From NH_4VO_3 : (Found: V, 8.58; N, 14.80%). χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1242$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.72$ B.M.

The following compounds were obtained by the interaction of aqueous vanadyl sulphate and the respective reagents.

3. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-benzoylphenyl-3-phenyltriazene-vanadium* (IV) was obtained in aqueous ethanol medium as yellowish green crystals. (Found: V, 7.22; N, 11.73. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)_2]$ requires V, 7.29; N, 12.01%). χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1856$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.11$ B.M.

4. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-nitrophenyl-3-phenyltriazene-vanadium* (IV) was obtained in aqueous acetone medium under mechanical stirring as a yellowish green powder; it was washed repeatedly with hot acetone. (Found: N, 19.60. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_3)_2]$ requires N, 19.27%). χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1376$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.82$ B.M.

5. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-sulphnamidophenyl-3-phenyltriazene-vanadium* (IV) was obtained as greenish yellow crystals. (Found: V, 7.43; N, 16.8. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{S})_2]$ requires V, 7.86; N, 17.25%).

6. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-carboxyphenyl-3-phenyltriazene-vanadium* (IV) was obtained as a leaf-green compound from ethanol-acetone mixture. (Found: V, 8.60; N, 14.25. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3)_2]$ requires V, 8.80; N, 14.51%). χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1523$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.91$ B.M.

7. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-m-bromophenyl-3-phenyltriazene-vanadium* (IV) was obtained as a greenish yellow crystalline precipitate from aqueous ethanol medium. (Found: N, 13.05; M.W., 659. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{OBr})_2]$ requires N, 12.94%; M.W., 649). χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1421$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.85$ B.M.

8. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-phenyl-3-p-methylphenyltriazene-vanadium* (IV) was obtained from VOSO_4 and also from NH_4VO_3 in aqueous ethanol medium by following the procedure of (1).

(A). From VOSO_4 : {Found: V, 9.60; N, 16.30. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O})_2]$ requires V; 9.82; N, 16.18%}. χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1337$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.80$ B.M.

(B). From NH_4VO_3 : (Found: V, 9.70. N, 16.30%). χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1189$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.69$ B.M.

9. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-methylphenyl-3-p-methylphenyltriazeno-vanadium(IV)* was obtained as a deep olive-green crystalline substance. {Found: V, 9.50; N, 15.20. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O})_2]$ requires V, 9.32; N, 15.35%}. χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1302$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.78$ B.M.

10. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-nitrophenyl-3-p-methylphenyltriazeno-vanadium(IV)* was obtained as a yellowish green powder in aqueous ethanol-acetone medium. This was washed repeatedly with acetone. {Found: N, 18.50. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)_2]$ requires N, 18.39%}. χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1093$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.63$ B.M.

11. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-phenyl-3-methyltriazeno-vanadium(IV)*: {Found: V, 13.60; N, 22.72; M.W., 355. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}_3\text{O})_2]$ requires V, 13.89; N, 22.88%; M.W., 367}. χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1023$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.58$ B.M.

12. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-methylphenyl-3-methyltriazeno-vanadium(IV)*: {Found: V, 12.50; N, 20.93; M.W., 394. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_3\text{O})_2]$ requires V, 12.91; N, 21.26%; M.W., 395}. χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1251$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.75$ B.M.

13. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-ethoxyphenyl-3-methyltriazeno-vanadium(IV)*.—From aqueous ethanol the compound was initially obtained as a curdy apple-green precipitate which was digested on a water bath, filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried as usual. {Found: V, 11.23; N, 18.32. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)_2]$ requires V, 11.21; N, 18.46%}. χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1175$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.69$ B.M.

14. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1- α -naphthyl-3-methyltriazeno-vanadium(IV)* was obtained as a brownish green-coloured compound. {Found: V, 10.68; N, 17.72. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O})_2]$ requires V, 10.92; N, 17.98%}. χ_m (corr.) $\times 10^6 = 1188$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.70$ B.M.

15. *Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-nitrophenyl-3-methyltriazeno-vanadium(IV)*: {Found: N, 24.40. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)_2]$ requires N, 24.50%}.

16. *Pyridine-dioxo-mono-3-hydroxy-1-p-methylphenyl-3-phenyltriazeno-vanadium(V)*:

(A). *Golden yellow variety*.—The quadrivalent oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1-p-methylphenyl-3-phenyltriazeno, prepared as described earlier, was treated with distilled pyridine. The latter on warming for a few minutes dissolved, yielding a brown solution from which the golden yellow to bright yellow crystals were obtained on cooling in ice-water. These were filtered, washed with cold ethanol, and dried over CaCl_2 . The compound is soluble in ethanol, producing a golden yellow colour, but in benzene, acetone etc. the colour changes to green on keeping. {Found: V, 12.90; N, 14.60. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N})]$ requires V, 13.14; N, 14.43%}. $\chi_g = -0.16 \times 10^{-6}$.

The golden yellow compound suffered no loss on heating at 100° for 10 hours although the colour changed to brownish green. (Found: V, 12.85%).

(B). *Dark green variety*.—The above golden yellow compound was dissolved in a large volume of benzene when the yellow colour changed to green after few minutes. The green

solution was filtered after allowing it to stand for a couple of hours and then evaporated to dryness. (Found: V, 13.25; N, 14.20%). $\chi_g = -0.18 \times 10^{-6}$.

17. *Pyridine-dioxo-mono-3-hydroxy-1-p-nitrophenyl-3-phenyltriazeno-vanadium(v)* was obtained as above from the preparation of (4) and distilled pyridine (10 ml) by refluxing on a water bath for about 45 minutes. The bright yellow crystalline compound was washed well with acetone. The compound is less soluble in benzene. (Found: V, 11.83; N, 16.59. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N})]$ requires V, 12.18; N, 16.70%). $\chi_g = -0.604 \times 10^{-6}$.

18. *Pyridine-dioxo-mono-3-hydroxy-1-phenyl-3-p-methylphenyltriazeno-vanadium(v)* was prepared by following the method of 16(A), starting from the corresponding vanadium (IV) complex. (Found: V, 12.95; N, 14.58; M.W., 405. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O})(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$ requires V, 13.14; N, 14.43%; M.W., 398). $\chi_g = -0.18 \times 10^{-6}$.

19. *Pyridine-dioxo-mono-3-hydroxy-1-p-methylphenyl-3-methyltriazeno-vanadium(v): Yellow variety.*—It was prepared by following earlier methods by heating on a water bath the corresponding vanadium(IV) complex and distilled pyridine (2-5 ml) for about 20 to 30 minutes. The dark red-brown solution deposited yellow crystals on cooling. (Found: V, 15.45; N, 17.00. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O})(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{N})]$ requires V, 15.64; N, 17.17%). $\chi_g = -0.16 \times 10^{-6}$. The golden yellow variety lost pyridine after heating at 100° for 15 hours, the colour changing to light bottle-green. (Found: V, 20.70%).

19A. *Dioxo-mono-3-hydroxy-1-p-methylphenyl-3-methyltriazeno-vanadium(v): Bottle-green variety.*—The above yellow compound was dissolved in benzene and allowed to stand for 2 to 4 hours. The green solution deposited a light bottle-green precipitate which was filtered and washed well with benzene. The product gave analyses indicating absence of pyridine. (Found: V, 20.35; N, 17.20. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O})]$ requires V, 20.64; N, 17.00%). $\chi_g = -0.06 \times 10^{-6}$.

20. *Pyridine-dioxo-mono-3-hydroxy-1-p-ethoxyphenyl-3-methyltriazeno-vanadium(v)* was obtained as an orange-yellow, hard, crystalline compound, following the method of (19). The compound is less soluble in benzene. (Found: V, 14.20; N, 15.81. $[(\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{N})]$ requires V, 14.32; N, 15.73%). $\chi_g = -0.17 \times 10^{-6}$. The orange-yellow compound lost pyridine on heating at 100° for 16 hours and the colour changed to brownish green. (Found: V, 18.8. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)]$ requires V, 18.40%).

Magnetic Measurements.—The magnetic moments were determined by the Gouy method, using a semimicro Mettler balance for measuring the difference in weight and with a field strength of 9.26×10^3 gauss. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood⁵.

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